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Trade Receivables Management And Profitability Of Consumer Goods Manufacturing Firms In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of trade receivables management on the profitability of consumer goods manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group Ltd. Trade receivables management was operationalized by accounts receivables size, accounts receivable collection period, and accounts receivable turnover, while profitability was determined by computing return on assets. The study relied on the transaction cost theory as its anchor, and collected data from thirteen consumer goods firms for eleven years (2012 to 2022), giving rise to 143 firm-year observations. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation and regression technique. Findings showed that accounts receivables size, accounts receivable collection period, and accounts receivable turnover, each had a negative effect on profitability. The study therefore recommended reduction in accounts receivables size, accounts receivable collection period, and accounts receivable turnover, in consonance with transaction cost theory.

Keywords: Accounts receivables size, accounts receivable collection period, accounts receivable turnover, profitability, return on assets, trade receivables management.

1. INTRODUCTION

In a market economy, the maximization shareholders' wealth and the sustenance of good financial performance are among the primary objectives of firms. To maximize the wealth of shareholders, managers strive for the efficient management of all the resources available to the firm, including trade receivables and borrowed funds. Trade receivables arise from credit sales made to the customers of a firm in accordance with the credit terms of the firm. Managers must of necessity manage trade receivables efficiently and effectively to avoid liquidity problems and ensure profitability. Trade receivables management refers to all management decisions and actions that ordinarily influence the size and effectiveness of the accounts receivables. This entails the exercise of managerial functions of planning, organizing, directing and control over trade receivables. The cardinal objective of trade receivables management is to boost firm financial performance and corporate liquidity. Unfortunately, profitability may be inversely related to liquidity. This makes trade receivables management challenging. Managers are faced with a dilemma of a trade-off between profitability and liquidity. This is made more complex because trade receivables management addresses the ramifications of practices and processes cutting

across several functional units or departments such as marketing, sales, finance and productions. Eliciting support of other managers outside the accounts and/finance department could be difficult because of variations in departmental objectives.

Since trade receivables are created from credit sales, managers must determine who, when and how to grant credit sales. To this end credit policy is critical to effective trade receivables management (Bringham & Houston, 2019). Bringham and Houston (2019) define credit policy as a set of rules that include the firm's credit period, discounts, credit standards, and collection procedures offered. Van Horne and Wachowicz (2008) note that trade credit is one of the many factors that can have a significant influence on a firm's sales. They explain that if a firm's competitors extend credit liberally and a firm does not, the firm policy may have a dampening effect on the firm's marketing effort. Liberal credit policy could boost sales and, by so doing, increase the recycling of funds and generating higher incomes. Increased sales could require enlargement of credit department, more clerical work in checking additional accounts, and servicing the added volume of receivables, increased probability of bad-debt losses deductible from profit, and may cause certain existing customers to be less conscientious about paying their bills on time. On the other hand, conservative credit policy could lead to high inventory with associated holding cost and reduced liquidity that could ultimately lead to bankruptcy. Increased credit sales suggest funds are tied up in accounts receivable and a company may find itself borrowing funds to finance operations. Borrowed funds attract interest which also affects profit negatively. Granting an extended collection period delays cash inflow which impair the firm's liquidity position and increases the chances of bad debt losses with ultimate negative which adverse impact on the financial performance (Pandey, 2004). It is equally argued that long average collection period could result to reduced recycling of funds which would, in turn, affect profitability and liquidity of the firm (Madishetti & Kibona (2013). Severe liquidity problems traceable to so much funds held in accounts receivable may lead to total collapse in production since the firm can no longer meet its financial obligations, which in extreme cases may lead to bankruptcy. There is also the contention of opportunity cost of committing funds to the investment in additional trade receivables instead of to some other investments.

Managing trade receivable involves a trade-off between profitability and liquidity. Effective trade receivables management is a continual balancing act in the light of various variables involved and the important influence on the company's value. The effect of trade receivables management on financial performance of firms is of a continuing interest to shareholders, managers and other stakeholders

Prior studies on working capital management and indeed trade receivables and their effect on financial performance produced mixed results. While some studies suggest a positive relationship (e.g. Mathuva, 2010), others documented a negative association (Deloof, 2003; Falope & Ajilore, 2009). Yet some studies failed to find any effect of working capital management or trade receivables management on financial performance (Abdullahi & Opeyemi, 2020; Ahmadi *et al.*, 2014). The mixed results could be because of varying factors such as the heterogeneity of industry characteristics and variations in operating environment. Some studies in the Nigerian context did not control for other factors that could affect financial performance (e.g. Jonah *et al.*, 2022). This study was conducted to clarify results and fill gap in literature.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

Trade receivables

Trade receivables are receivables generated by a firm from its ordinary course of business such as sale of goods or supply of services to customers. On the other hand, non-trade receivables are any other type of receivables such as amounts owed to the company by its employees for personal purchased made on their behalf. Comparatively, non-trade receivables are quite smaller than trade receivables. Trade receivables is alternatively called account receivables. Van Horne and Wachowicz (2008. p. 250) refer to accounts receivables as the 'amounts of money owed to a firm by customers who have bought goods or services on credit'. Put differently, when a firm sells goods or renders services on credit, the customer is given

time within which the customer makes payment. Thus, the payment outstanding is referred to as trade receivables. It is therefore clear that trade receivables arise from credit sales (Paul *et al.* 2018). They state that accounts receivables occur when suppliers of goods and services sell on credit and allow their customers to defer payment to a later date.

Accounts receivables indicates the proportion of cash that is held up in unpaid invoices dispatched to clients. It is a significant component of current assets. Though it is not depicted as line item in the Statement of Financial Position of a firm, it is usually shown in the Notes to the Account. When a firm sells goods or renders a service to a customer, the firm issues an invoice. The invoice specifies amongst other things the amount the client is owing. The firm creates an accounts receivable in the General Ledger wherein the customer is debited and Sales Account is credited. Thus, accounts receivable is an accounting term for money a firm expects from clients who have been issued invoices for goods supplied or services rendered but which the clients have not made payment. Analysis of trade receivables reveals which client owes the firm money and how much. Trade receivable is very important for cash flow management as it gives a good indication of liquidity or financial health of firms.

Profitability

Profitability is a measure of the extent to which a business has efficiently deployed its resources to obtain financial gain. It is one of the most important and pervasive measure of financial performance. The operationalize profitability, businesses and researchers compute metrics such as return on assets (Chukwu & Egbunike, 2017), return on equity, earnings per share and return on investments (Davies *et al.*, 2023; Chukwu & Wadike, 2018; Iloma & Chukwu, 2023; Osirim *et al.*, 2021). In this study, profitability was determined using return on assets.

2.2. Theoretical Foundation

The theoretical foundation of this study is the Transactions Costs Theory which was developed by Schwartz (1974) and discussed in detail by Ferris (1981). The theory discusses trade credit. Trade credit gives rise to trade receivables. Transaction costs denote those expenses borne in the course of arranging, managing, and monitoring various activities across the markets. The theory stipulates that the minimization of ordering and carrying cost of inventory may affect investment in receivables; thus, reduction in transactional cost of paying bills and reduction in accounts receivable period as a form of accounts receivable management will enhance firm profitability. From the perspective of the buyer, rather than paying bills as soon as items are delivered, a customer with credit sales accumulates responsibilities and pays them only at agreed-upon intervals which could be weekly, monthly, or quarterly. The vendor would also be able to decouple the payment cycle from the delivery timetable in this way. This will reduce costs of transactions such as bank charges as banks charge businesses on a per transaction basis. Transaction cost theory has been used to explain production of goods, inventory management and trade credit (Mian & Smith, 1992).

Firms manufacturing goods with a high degree of seasonality in their consumption patterns may in a bid to maintain smooth production cycles, build up large inventories, which will result in stock warehousing costs and tied-down capital. The firm could cut these costs by (a) lowering the price of the goods to encourage early sales and demand. Transaction Cost Theory argues that credit should be advanced to customers and customers should be allowed to pay at a later date thus reducing the transaction costs and establishment of affordable payment pattern. Using transactions costs, Emery (1987) argues that when demand fluctuates, a better decision could be taken by the seller by changing trade credit terms. Terms can be relaxed when demand drops and tightened when demand increases. Studies such as Ezejiofor *et al.*, 2015 and Nwanna and Oguezue (2017) have provided support to the Transaction Cost Theory.

2.3. Empirical review and hypotheses

A number of studies have examined the relationship between trade receivables and other variables such as financial performance and board characteristics, using trade receivables as predictor or criterion variable. Yegon *et al.* (2022) argued that corporate failure among companies in Kenya has often been associated

with their financial management decisions. One area of financial management is the management of accounts receivables. The study conducted an analysis of a panel dataset extracted from annual reports of 40 tea firms located in Kenya for the period 2014 to 2019. The results indicated a significant negative relationship between accounts receivables in days and the financial performance of the sampled firms, indicating that a decrease in the accounts receivables collection period would lead to a rise in the return on assets.

Olayemi (2021), explored the effect of working capital management on financial performance using data obtained from the annual financial reports of ten companies in the health and food and beverages sectors listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange from 2012– 2019, Working capital management as independent variable has the following components: average collection period, average payments period, inventory turnover in days, and cash conversion cycle. Return on assets was the measure of financial performance. The result of the regression analyses showed that average collection period has positive and significant effect on firm performance.

Ebirien and Chukwu (2022) explored the effect of board characteristics on trade receivables. The attributes considered were board size, board independence, board gender diversity and board shareholdings. The study used data extracted from the annual reports of a sample of 13 Nigerian listed consumer goods manufacturing firms for the period 2012 to 2020 and utilized accounts collection period as the proxy of trade receivables management. Relying on agency theory, the study formulated four null hypotheses and tested them by estimating Ordinary Least Square Regression Model. Findings showed that board size, and board shareholdings have positive effect on trade receivables management, while the other predictors did not have any significant effect on trade receivables management. The study therefore recommended that Nigerian listed consumer goods manufacturing firms should encourage more board shareholdings and scale up their board size. Also, the appointment of females and non-executive directors into corporate boards should be based on the competence on the appointees, not merely to satisfy societal expectations or legal requirements.

Abdullahi and Opeyemi (2020) undertook an analysis of the effect of working capital management on the profitability of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The study sought to determine the extent to which number of days account receivables, inventory, and number of days of account payable affects return on asset (ROA) of consumer goods companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange over covers a period of 5 years from 2014-2018. Out of a population of 24 consumer goods companies listed on Nigerian Stock Exchange, the study selected thirteen firms as sample size. It obtained data from the annual reports and accounts of sampled companies. Aided with the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20, the study performed test of hypotheses using multiple regression analysis. The study reported a negative and insignificant influence of trade receivable collection period and trade payable payment period on ROA while inventory conversion period has a positive insignificant effect on ROA of consumer goods companies.

Based on the mixed findings from prior research, and the predictors of the current research, this study formulated the following hypotheses.

Ho₁: Accounts receivable size does not have a significant effect on the return on assets of Nigerian listed consumer goods manufacturing firms.

Ho₂: Accounts receivable period does not have a significant influence on the return on the assets of Nigerian listed consumer goods manufacturing firms.

Ho₃: Accounts receivable turnover does not have a significant effect on the return on assets of Nigerian listed consumer goods manufacturing firms.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Accounting researchers often use ex-post facto research design, a form of quasi-experimental research design, which focuses on events that have already taken place in the past and utilizes secondary data for analysis (Kumar, 2011). Considering the objective of this study and unit of analysis, this study used ex-post facto research design. The population of the study consists of 20 firms listed in the Consumer Goods

Sector of the Nigerian Exchange Group in 2022. The study employed census sampling technique in selecting the sample. Under this technique, every element in the population is also in the sample. This approach was adopted because the number of firms in the population was relatively small. However, six firms in the population did not have a complete data set, and were therefore excluded from the sample. This gave rise to a sample size of 13 firms. Data were collected from the annual reports of the selected firms from 2012 to 2022 - a period of eleven years. The final sample is therefore a balanced panel dataset of 143 firm-year observations.

Data obtained from the sampled firms were analysed using univariate analysis, bivariate and multivariate analysis. At the heart of univariate analysis is descriptive statistics. In the bivariate analysis, the study carried out a correlation analysis. The primary objective of correlation analysis was to establish the magnitude of the correlation coefficient to assess the presence or absence of multicollinearity. For the purpose of the multivariate estimation the following model was used.

$$ROA_{j,t} = \Psi_0 + \Psi_1 ARZ_{j,t} + \Psi_2 ACP_{j,t} + \Psi_3 ATR_{j,t} + \Psi_4 BS_{j,t} + \Psi_5 CCR_{j,t} + \Psi_6 APP_{j,t} + \Psi_7 INVT_{j,t} + \Psi_8 LEV_{j,t} + \varepsilon_{j,t}$$

Where for firm j at year t:

ROA = Return on Assets.

ARZ =Accounts Receivable Size.

ACP = Accounts Receivable Collection Period.

ATR = Accounts Receivable Turnover.

BS = Board Size

CCR = Current Ratio

APP = Average Trade Payable Period

INV = Inventory Turnover

LEV = Leverage

ε = Error term

Ψ_0 = Intercept.

$\Psi_1 \dots \Psi_3$ = Regression parameters

ε = Error term

The model consists of a dependent variable (ROA), three independent variables (ARZ, ACP, ATR) and five control variables (BS, CCR, APP, INV and LEV). Prior studies have shown that a wide range of factors affect financial performance. To properly assess the effect of trade receivables on financial performance it is reasonable to introduce these variables in the regression model as control variables.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.1. Univariate and bivariate analysis

Table 4.1 contains a univariate analysis of 143 firm-year observations. The mean value of ROA is 0.0673004. This suggests that on average firms in the sample earned approximately 7kobo from total assets. With a range from -0.1965952 to 0.3152346, the standard deviation is 0.0833043 suggesting less variability amongst the firms. Table 4.1 shows mean of ROE as of 0.2156129 with a standard deviation 0.3638876. The standard deviation indicates considerable dispersion amongst the sample. Table 4.1 recorded a mean of 0.0508824 and a standard deviation of 0.111953 in respect of NPM. This suggests a 5k net profit per N100 sales. The maximum NPM is 0.2490982

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ROA	143	0.0673004	0.083304	-0.196595	0.3152346
ARZ	143	0.5156991	1.479395	0.0002845	8.99732
ACP	143	26.1328	26.82041	2.112844	256.3241
ATR	143	31.15907	34.99907	1.306286	238.5429
BS	143	10.47552	2.279215	7	15
CCR	143	1.235839	1.477681	0.3471242	13.51549
APP	143	41.03702	36.05754	4.826742	299.9377
INV	143	88.55229	48.04241	17.49111	343.09
LEV	143	0.8182577	1.110099	0.0583205	13.515

Source: Researcher's computation, 2023

On the average, firms in the sample held 52% of their sales as credit sales. There is considerable dispersion in the ARZ as suggested by the standard deviation. The average number of days it took the firms to collect payment from trade debtors is 26 days with the maximum standing at 256 days. The maximum of ACP is indicative of existence of delinquent trade debtors. Sample firms on the average settled their trade creditor 41 days which is more than the mean of ACP. The mean turnover rate is 31 times. The standard deviation points at wide dispersions amongst the sample.

Table 4.2 Correlation Matrix for Model 2 (ROA)

	ROA	ARZ	ACP	ATR	BS	CCR	APP	INV	LEV
ROA	1.000								
ARZ	-0.269*	1.000							
ACP	-0.126	-0.080	1.000						
ATR	-0.122	0.119	-0.456*	1.000					
BS	-0.241*	-0.014	-0.140	0.035	1.000				
CCR	-0.327*	0.313*	-0.152	0.284*	0.018	1.000			
APP	-0.069	-0.043	0.013	-0.118	0.113	0.087	1.000		
INV	-0.204*	0.0303	0.267*	-0.236*	0.103	-0.141	-0.044	1.000	
LEV	-0.244*	0.0511	-0.095	0.180*	-0.051	0.682*	0.056	-0.062	1.000

Source: Researcher's computation, 2024

* denotes 5% level of significance

4.2. Test of hypotheses

The study presents the results of estimating the empirical models specified above. The results of Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity as ($\chi^2(1) = 3.62$; Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.0571$) suggest that there is no serious issue of heteroskedasticity with the ROA model. The Model Summary in Table 4.3, Table 4.8 and Table 4.9, and Table 4.10 shows that the study used 143 firm-year observations to estimate the Models. The p-value of the F statistics in Table 4.7, Table 4.8 and Table 4.9, and Table 4.10 shows that the Models have good fit. The coefficient of determination in Table 4.7 is 0.2995 which suggests that approximately 30% of variations in return on assets were jointly explained by the independent variables as well as the control variables. In Table 4.8, it was observed that 13% variations in return on equity were jointly explained by the independent variable and control variables. In contrast, Table 4.9 reports R-squared statistics of 0.5862. This indicates that approximately 59% variations in net profit margin were jointly explained by the independent variables and control variables. The R-squared statistics 0.2289 reported in Table 4.10 suggests that trade receivables management, firm size, the interaction term as well as the control variables account for 23% variations in the financial performance of Nigerian listed consumer goods manufacturing firms. The control variables in Table 4.7, Table 4.8, Table 4.9, and Table 4.10 are board size (BS), current ratio (CCR), average payment period (APP), inventory turnover (INV), and leverage (LEV).

Table 4.3 Regression Results

ROA	Coef.	Std. Err.	T	p-value
ARZ	-0.0115018	0.0044569	-2.58	0.011
ACP	-0.0007771	0.0002607	-2.98	0.003
ATR	-0.0004261	0.0002032	-2.10	0.038
BS	-0.0091406	0.0027364	-3.34	0.001
CCR	-0.0104441	0.0062526	-1.67	0.097
APP	-0.0001231	0.0001717	-0.72	0.475
INV	-0.0003176	0.0001345	-2.36	0.020
LEV	-0.0089401	0.0076905	-1.16	0.247
CONS	0.2559667	0.0332712	7.69	0.000
Model Summary				
Number of obs	143			
F(8, 134)	7.16			
Prob > F	0.0000			
R-squared	0.2995			

Source: Researcher's computation, 2024

The result of test of H_{01} in Table 4.3 shows that the coefficient on ARZ is negative ($\Psi_1 = -0.0115018$) with test statistics of -2.58 and a p-value of 0.011. Therefore hypothesis 1 is rejected. This means that accounts receivable size has a significant effect on the return on assets of Nigerian listed consumer goods manufacturing firms. The result of test of H_{02} in Table 4.3 shows that the coefficient on ACP is negative ($\Psi_2 = -0.0007771$) and t statistics of -2.98 and a p-value of 0.003. Therefore H_{02} is rejected since the p-value of test statistics is less than 0.05. This means that accounts receivable period has a significant influence on the return on the assets of Nigerian listed consumer goods manufacturing firms. The result of test of H_{03} in Table 4.3 shows that the coefficient on ART is negative ($\Psi_3 = -0.0004261$) and t statistics of -2.10 and a p-value of 0.038. Therefore, H_{03} is rejected since the p-value of test statistics is less than 0.05. Therefore, accounts receivable turnover has a significant effect on the return on assets of Nigerian listed consumer goods manufacturing firms.

4.3. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study revealed a negative coefficient on accounts receivables size ($\Psi_1 = -0.0115018$) in Table 4.3. The relationship is significant at the 1% level (p-value = 0.011). This finding concurs with Falope and Ajilore, (2009). Increase in account receivables could lead to increased bad debts which could impact financial performance negatively. Findings from the multivariate analysis in Table 4.3 shows that the coefficient on accounts receivable period (ACP) is negative ($\Psi_2 = -0.0007771$). This relationship is significant as shown by the probability value of 0.003. The finding aligns with Yegon *et al.* (2022). It is however in disagreement with Mathuva (2010). The study found that accounts receivable turnover has a constraining effect on return on assets. Overall, the implication of the findings is consistent with transaction costs theory which stipulates that the minimization of ordering and carrying cost of inventory may affect investment in receivables; thus, reduction in transactional cost of paying bills and reduction in accounts receivable period as a form of accounts receivable management will enhance firm profitability. This is because of the negative relationship between trade receivables and financial performance.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study was motivated by the need to clarify research on the effect of trade receivables on the financial performance of listed consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria, given the mixed findings from prior research. Three hypotheses were formulated and tested, and data from thirteen firms for eleven years were analyzed using the regression technique. Results showed that accounts receivable size, accounts receivable period, and accounts receivable turnover, each had a negative effect on financial performance,

suggesting that increases in each of the variable will reduce the financial performance of the reporting entity. Firms must therefore strive to reduce accounts receivable size, accounts receivable period, and accounts receivable turnover, to enhance profitability.

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